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Research article

Brood protection is essential but not sufficient for population survival of lapwings *Vanellus vanellus* in central Switzerland

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Lapwing are among those ground nesting bird species that suffered strong population declines following agricultural intensification in many parts of Europe. The key problem appears to be a low breeding success which, depending on the situation, may be due to predation of eggs and chicks, starvation of chicks especially during dry conditions, agricultural activities leading to direct killings, and suboptimal breeding habitat. Here, we report on a population of 40–60 lapwing breeding pairs in an intensively cultivated arable landscape in central Switzerland, where protection from farming activities, implementation of special lapwing habitat and nest fencing to exclude terrestrial predators (mainly red fox) started in 2005 and is still ongoing. Chicks were ringed and families subsequently observed every 2–3 days. Hatching success for fenced nests built before May was high. Low hatching success was observed in unfenced nests due to high predation rates and in late nests due to abandonment by the female when the vegetation was growing too tall (e.g. maize). Regularly, chicks disappeared during the night shortly after hatching. Most likely many of them first left the fence and were predated outside. Our observations from a fenced field with wet soils and puddles suggest that lapwing may produce sufficient offspring if predation can be reduced and if large enough areas with suitable habitat are available.

Keywords: breeding success, chick survival, Lapwing, predation, *Vanellus vanellus*

Introduction

Ground-nesting bird species in agricultural areas suffered strong declines in recent decades, due to major habitat changes following large-scale introduction of new agricultural practices (Newton 2004, Shrubbs 2007, Berthold et al. 2017). These included drainage of wet soils and intensive production using more fertilizers and pesticides as well as heavy and fast-operating machines working in an increasingly homogeneous landscape. Prominent examples of declining species in Europe are Eurasian skylark *Alauda arvensis* (Siriwardena et al. 2002), corncrake *Crex crex* (Green et al. 1997), and waders such as black-tailed godwit *Limosa limosa* and northern lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* (Trolliet 2003, Thorup 2006, Shrubbs 2007). For ground-nesting species, a first

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pre-condition for population survival is to prevent excessive losses due to direct killing by modern agricultural machinery. Given enough resources, this can be achieved, via for instance marking nests, informing farmers, postponing farming activities, and compensatory payments to farmers (Seymour et al. 2003, Gruebler et al. 2012, Plard et al. 2020, Cimiotti et al. 2022). Such measures have been implemented for species that are conspicuous and (locally) rare enough to raise public and political awareness, like for the species mentioned above. However, often such measures were not sufficient for population survival, not even when combined with habitat improvements, e.g. for the northern lapwing (Ausden et al. 2009, Malpas et al. 2013, Franks et al. 2018).

Northern lapwing ('lapwing' henceforth) populations have declined by 64% in Europe between 1980 and 2019 (BirdLife International 2022). A decrease by 90% has been seen in Germany between 1992 and 2016 (Gerlach et al. 2019), by 49% in England and Wales between 1987 and 1998 (Wilson et al. 2001) or by 89% between 1987 and 2013 in Northern Ireland (Colhoun et al. 2015). In Switzerland, the population decreased from at least 1000 pairs in the 1970s (Birrer and Schmid 1989) to a minimum of 83 pairs in 2005 (Sattler et al. 2009). However, the 1000 pairs in the 1970s marked an intermezzo population recovery following earlier declines. This intermezzo population – often breeding on arable land, while before breeding was more limited to different types of wetland – had a very low reproductive success and depended heavily on immigration (Matter 1982, Schifferli et al. 2009), which apparently receded eventually.

With the shift to more breeding on intensively used agricultural land, such as arable fields, around the middle of the 20th century, lapwings faced a new set of problems compared to earlier populations: Lack of sufficient food for chicks on drained arable land during periods of low rain (Matter 1982, Beintema et al. 1991, Eglington et al. 2010), destruction of eggs and chicks by agricultural machinery, and a lack of semi-open habitat with low vegetation during the incubation period of first and replacement clutches. In addition, predation, especially mammalian predation, appears to have increased in the last decades in Switzerland as well as other areas in Europe, presumably as a consequence of habitat changes, reduced culling of red fox *Vulpes vulpes* and the eradication of rabies (extinct in Switzerland by 1999) that had reduced fox populations periodically (Chamberlain and Crick 2003, Langgemach and Bellebaum 2005, MacDonald and Bolton 2008, Roodbergen et al. 2012, Mason et al. 2018).

In view of the strong decline of lapwing populations in Europe, it is critical to understand drivers behind this development. There seems to be no evidence for reduced survival of adult birds (Roodbergen et al. 2012, Souchay and Schaub 2016). Rather, reduced breeding productivity seems to be the main driver of the negative population trends (Matter 1982, Schekkerman et al. 2009, Roodbergen et al. 2012, Plard et al. 2020).

To better understand what drives population development of lapwings breeding on agricultural land, we closely followed a lapwing population in central Switzerland. This population

had declined from about 40–60 pairs in the 1950s to 15 pairs around 2005 (Schifferli et al. 2009), when focused conservation measures were first implemented. Nests were marked with sticks to prevent destruction by agricultural activity. The breeding sites were fenced to exclude terrestrial predators – mainly red fox – since it was hypothesized that low reproductive success was the most likely reason for the population decline. We observed hatching and fledging success to investigate whether these conservation measures were successful (Schifferli et al. 2009). The population increased to 60 pairs in 2015 (Fig. 1, solid line), but since then decreased to 39 breeding pairs in 2021. In this article, we focus on the effects of fencing and other covariates on hatching and fledging success during the years 2006–2021.

Material and methods

Study site

The study area 'Plain of Wauwil' is an 18 km² flat area at 500 m a.s.l. in central Switzerland (47°10'22"N, 08°01'06"E) bordered by hills rising to 600–700 m a.s.l.. The western half of the area, where most lapwings breed, is a former marshland, gradually drained until the Second World War and now managed as intensive meadows (about 35% of the agriculturally used area, up to six cuts year⁻¹), maize (24%), winter grain (16%), medium intensive meadows (14%, up to three cuts year⁻¹), pastures, rape, potatoes and vegetables (2–3% each). A few farm buildings, some small woods (2% of the total area) and a power line are the only large vertical structures. An overland road (speed limit 80 km h⁻¹) crosses the area. Many small roads, most with a motor vehicle ban and typically around 200 m apart, allow access for farmers and leisure visitors such as hikers, dog walkers and cyclists. To increase breeding opportunities, 'lapwing fallows' were installed since 2011. For this, 1–3 fields covering 1–4.5 ha in total were sown in late summer with non-perennial plants and left as a fallow until the following July.

Figure 1. Development of the lapwing breeding population in the plain of Wauwil (dark line), the area fenced to protect nests and some of the feeding area (thin line, right outer axis), and the proportion of nests inside a fence (dots, right inner axis) from 2005–2021. Depending on how concentrated the lapwings were nesting, a given fenced area included a smaller or larger proportion of all nests.

Study species

The northern lapwing is a medium-sized wader (adult weight 150–300 g) distributed over most of Europe and parts of Asia (Trolliet 2003, Shrubbs 2007). In Europe, most lapwings migrate to the Mediterranean area for wintering and return in early spring to the breeding grounds. In our study area, lapwings mostly arrive at the end of February and beginning of March to breed on fields, stubbles and wet meadows. The semi colonial ground breeder needs long periods (ca 75 days in March–July) with little disturbance and semi-open and late-growing crops for successful breeding and raising the chicks (Shrubbs 2007).

After arrival at the breeding sites, males defend small territories against other males and court towards females. Males build several little depressions in the ground as potential nest sites. Females inspect males and territories and nest building starts, taking around 2–10 days. Then, four eggs are laid and incubated mainly by the female for 25–27 days (Galbraith 1988, Shrubbs 2007). Chicks leave the nest shortly after hatching. The adult birds, mainly females, lead their chicks to good foraging habitats, mostly wet meadows, fields and semi-open areas, ideally with wet soils or puddles. The family often remains in the vicinity of the nest site, but some wander many 100 m away during the chick rearing phase (Shrubbs 2007, Rickenbach et al. 2011). Avian (e.g. carrion crow *Corvus corone*, red kite *Milvus milvus*, common kestrel *Falco tinnunculus*) as well as ground predators (e.g. red fox, domestic cat, stoat *Mustela erminea*) are attacked or lured away when coming too close to nests or chicks. In this way, avian predators are often successfully cast away from an area of about 30–50 m around the nest (Elliot 1985), especially if several pairs breed in close vicinity (Seymour et al. 2003, MacDonald and Bolton 2008, Eglington et al. 2009), while such defence against mammalian predators such as foxes seems to be less effective (Korner et al. unpubl.). Until the age of 10–15 days, chicks are brooded regularly, especially during night and cold and wet weather. Thermal independence is reached around age 21–25 days (Beintema and Visser 1989a, b). At around 30–35 days, chicks fledge.

Fencing, ringing and field observation protocol

Nests were discovered by observing male and female courtship, nest building or incubation. Nests with eggs were marked with numbered bamboo sticks placed 2–5 m away from the nest to prevent destruction by agricultural activity. Electric fences were generally set up in areas where two or more nests were found within 100 m on the same field. On average, fenced areas were around 1 ha so that, ideally, more females joined the first two breeding females and the fence eventually encompassed up to 25 nests. We also regularly fenced fields without nests but where several families were foraging for several days. Nevertheless, chicks wandering around regularly left fences or switched between the inside and the outside of a fence. In most years, over 80% of nests were fenced (Fig. 1, grey dots); not fenced nests were mostly

single nests on a field. Due to the intensive observation activity (the entire area was visited every 1–2 days) and due to the conspicuous behaviour of lapwings during courtship and for nest defence, we are confident that we missed only few nests and none or extremely few families with chicks.

Electric fences were orange (before 2018) or white (since 2018), 90–106 cm tall and consisted of a 10 cm mesh net with conductive horizontal strands except for the lowest strand, such that small animals, e.g. hedgehog, toad, as well as lapwing chicks can pass without harm. The fences, typically used for sheep pasturing, exclude mammals such as red fox, badger *Meles meles*, domestic cat and dog with few exceptions, but not smaller mammals (such as stoat) or aerial predators.

Nests were visited by us once during the breeding period during daytime after the fence was erected to determine the number of eggs (before 2018 sometimes more often to determine egg size and weight). Date of egg-laying was mostly known from the observation of freshly laid eggs, else it was inferred from the hatching date or, in a few cases, from the estimated age of observed chicks. Successful hatching was confirmed by the presence of chicks, which was often indicated by the warning female in the nest surroundings. Nest failure was indicated by the disappearance of the female, after which the nest was checked to confirm failure. Broken eggshells, yolk or traces of predators (fox traces) were an indication of predation, intact but cold eggs indicated abandonment. Some predation may have been secondary predation following abandonment, but we think this was not common, as, due to the dense observation activity, predation would have had to follow abandonment very quickly. Flooding and destruction by agricultural machinery were obvious.

Until 2018, most chicks were colour ringed at the age of 1–3 days (a few later). In addition, 49 adults (48 females, 1 male) were ringed. Since 2019, only 20–50% of the chicks were ringed because many pairs were breeding in very high density and ringing would have led to much disturbance. Families were observed using telescopes to determine chick survival. Every one to two days, each family identifiable by a ringed mother or by ringed chicks was searched, the number of remaining chicks (ringed or not) were counted and, if colour-ringed, the chicks were individually identified. In addition, we noted whether the family was inside or outside of a fence. Fledging was registered when chicks were able to fly more than just a few meters, generally around day 33. Sometimes, successful fledging was only confirmed when the colour-ringed individual was re-encountered post-fledging in the year of birth or in a following year.

Predictors

We use the term ‘incubation period’ for the time from egg laying to hatching or egg loss. To estimate the strength of communal nest defence, the number of active nests within 50 m was calculated. For this, we define a ‘nest start’ date five days before the first egg was laid and a ‘nest end’ date 10 days after hatching or until the loss of all eggs or chicks. This

period was chosen as it is assumed to be the period during which parents were close to the nest site and likely contributed to (communal) nest defence.

Table 1 lists the predictors used in the statistical models. Both for incubation and chick rearing we define one weather parameter which we judge especially relevant for the corresponding period: proportion of dry hours during the incubation period, and proportion of dry and warm (at least 15°C) hours during the first 15 chick days or the loss of all chicks. Regarding weather, these 15 days are critical when feathers of the chicks are not yet giving enough protection against cold and wet weather (Beintema and Visser 1989a).

For each nest, we registered the field type (agricultural usage). The field type of all fields in the study area was only known for summer and for the years 2011–2017 (data from the Department for Agriculture and Forest of the canton of Lucerne).

Statistical analyses

For the incubation period, we fitted three generalized additive binomial models (with logit-link function), one each for the outcome variable nest hatching success, probability of nest predation, and probability of nest abandonment ('incubation models'). Fledging success was modelled at the level of the individual chick using a multistate capture–recapture model ('fledging model').

Nest hatching success was binarized into less than vs at least half of the eggs hatched, since in 84% of the clutches either no or all eggs hatched. In all three incubation models, nest start date was included as a smoother due to its non-linear relationship with the outcome variable. Fence time, year, weather, and neighbours were used as continuous linear predictors, field type as fixed factor (Table 1). Year was also used as random

factor to account for non-independence among nests due to year-specific factors not taken into account otherwise. No model selection on the level of the main effects was conducted. Quadratic effects were added when residual plots (residual versus predictor value) suggested non-linearity. The interactions fence time × neighbours and fence time × year were included in the model, because we might expect a reduced fence-effect with more neighbours (due to communal colony defence), and because we were interested in potential changes of the fence-effect over the years (e.g. predators getting accustomed to the colony). Hatching success, probability of nest predation, and probability of nest abandonment are all interconnected; therefore, we used the same model structure for all three incubation models. These were fitted using the function *gam4* from the R-package 'gam4' (Wood and Scheipl 2017; using thin plate regression splines with default k-values for the smoothed date effect) in the R ver. 4.2.2 (www.r-project.org).

Model fit was graphically checked, e.g. observed versus fitted values (with observed mean values for binned fitted values in the case of binary outcome variables), bubble plots and semi-variograms for inspecting spatial autocorrelation (which was not indicated) and residual versus predictor plots to inspect the linearity assumption (Korner-Nievergelt et al. 2015). Inference was done using 95% uncertainty intervals from Bayesian posterior distributions returned by the function *sim* (which uses flat priors; R-package 'arm', Gelman and Su 2022).

We did not statistically correct for nests that failed but were never detected by us. Therefore, our absolute values of hatching success will overestimate the true value somewhat. Non-detection can be assumed to be larger for isolated, i.e. non-fenced nests and nests later in the season (with higher vegetation obscuring detection). As these nests had the least hatching probability, accounting for non-detection would accentuate the pattern.

Table 1. Predictors used in the models, including their arithmetic mean, range and 95% interquartil range. ¹log of value+1 used in the models; exp of mean log-value=1.9 (geometric mean), the value used for predictions in effect plots. ²includes unsown fields, potatoes, vegetables, wheat, and other crop, and artificial meadows in rotation with crop cultivation. ³mainly an area of extensive grassland with puddles of variable size depending on rainfall, and a few nests in sedge meadows.

Predictor	Description	Mean	Range	95%
Fence time	Proportion of incubation period (first egg laid until loss of all eggs or hatching) with fence	0.73	0–1	0–1
Nest start	Nest start date (5 days before first egg laid)	10 April	3 March–31 May	12 March–18 May
Hatch date	Date of hatching of chicks	16 May	14 April–25 June	18 April–18 June
Year	Year of breeding	2014.8	2006–2021	2006–2021
Weather (incubation models)	Proportion of dry hours (no precipitation) during incubation period	0.89	0.70–1	0.79–0.98
Weather (fledging model)	Proportion of dry (no precipitation) and warm (at least 15°C) hours during the first 15 chick days or until loss of all chicks	0.41	0–1	0–0.93
Neighbours	Mean number of active nests (five days before first egg laid until 10 days after hatching or loss of all eggs or chicks) within 50 m during the incubation period	2.9 ¹	0–16.5	0–11.8
Field type (at nest start)	Aggregated field types: cultivated field ² (n=382 clutches) fallow, stubbles (194) lapwing fallow (166) maize (150) extensive meadow (26) wet meadow ³ (97)			

The aim of the ‘fledging model’ was to describe the survival curve of chicks from hatching to fledging. We also explored effects of fence, hatch date, and weather condition (dry and warm, see Table 1) on chick survival. Fencing was done to protect the population rather than to collect data perfectly suitable for such analyses, e.g. there were almost no observed freshly hatched chicks outside a fence. Therefore, we interpret the results from the fledging model with extra caution.

In the fledging model, we estimate chick survival in three-day intervals (not daily survival due to limitations in the data), accounting for imperfect detection (for a detailed description of the model, see the Supporting information). The model is a multi-state model with six states: alive inside fence, alive outside fence, alive post-fledge, alive 2nd year (i.e. observed alive during the calendar year following birth), alive 3rd year or later, and dead. Using 3-day intervals for the 33-day fledging period, we therefore have a capture history with 14 timepoints, 11 for the hatching period and 3 afterwards (post-fledge, 2nd year, 3rd year+). For the 13 steps between the 14 timepoints, we estimated nine independent survival probabilities (same estimate for step 2 and 3, 4 and 5, 6 and 7, 8 and 9, due to limited data). A transition matrix describes the probabilities to change from one of the six states to the others. In this matrix, we first included a probability to move from inside to outside a fence or vice versa, then this probability was multiplied by survival. The same movement probability was estimated for the first two steps (i.e. chick age \leq six days), and another one for all following eight steps (up to fledging). After fledging, the fence status was no longer of importance and only survival was estimated (i.e. for the last three steps). Detection probabilities were estimated analogously to the survival estimates (nine independent values, although the last was confounded with survival by design).

Chicks observed only once and only before age 15 days most likely did not survive, given our large observation efforts. Therefore, in the model, the state of such chicks was set to dead for the last chick interval (timepoint 11). In years 2019–2021, ringing of young was strongly reduced to prevent disturbance of the colony, and chick survival was mainly deduced from observing families with ringed females. Because such chicks could not be identified post-fledging, their detection probability was set to 0 for the three timepoints after fledging, but if they were observed to be able to fly, their true state for post-fledge was set to ‘alive’ to inform the model that they survived chick-time. This was also done for a small number of ringed chicks able to fly around day 30 or re-encountered later from other sites.

In summary, the fledging model estimates separate survival for inside and outside a fence, for age classes (three-day chick age classes and three classes after hatching), and effects of hatch date and weather. Detection is estimated dependent on fence status and age class, and movement probability (between inside and outside fence) on age class. Year was included as a random factor for survival and detection.

The fence status of a chick for a timepoint (i.e. a three-day interval) was defined as the main side of the fence the chick was observed during this timepoint (ties were assigned

to ‘outside fence’). Since most nests were fenced, fence status was almost always ‘inside fence’ for the first timepoint (age 1–3 days). However, based on Rickenbach et al. (2011) and own observations (e.g. of entire families disappearing in one night), we believe that among the considerable number of chicks that disappeared shortly after hatching, a substantial proportion had left the fence and then was killed at night by ground predators. Yet, such chicks have the last fence status ‘inside fence’, leading to a bias in the fence state especially for the first timepoint. There is no way to account for this bias, but we present scenarios that assume that 20, 50 or 80% of the chicks seen only once at a young age actually died outside (rather than inside) a fence, as opposed to the 10.6% according to the raw data (= the ‘naive model’).

Results

Nesting habitat

Nests were often built on fallows (fields after harvesting and not yet re-cultivated or left aside for a year, typically covered by a sparse vegetation of low height) and unsown fields throughout the breeding season. At the beginning of the season, meadows and wheat fields were selected too, as long as their vegetation was low. Later in the season, potato fields and especially maize fields were selected in addition to fallows (Fig. 2).

For a comparison with the available fields, we only have data for the field types in summer, i.e. later than when nests are initiated. The strong preference of fallows compared to the availability as seen in Fig. 2, hence, is somewhat exaggerated, since maize in summer represents to some degree the availability of stubble and fallow in spring. Nevertheless, it is evident that the lapwings favoured open-ground habitats and deslected cultivated fields, extensive meadows, rape and pastures.

Hatching success

Of 1015 nests, 65.8% hatched, 16.5% were predated, 15.3% abandoned, 1.1% destroyed by agricultural activity, 0.5%

Figure 2. Available field types in the study area in summer (left-most stacked bar and left y-axis; average for the years 2011–2017; % of the agricultural land), and the field types used by lapwings for nesting per 10-day period across the breeding season (right y-axis, cumulative numbers for the years 2006–2021).

flooded and 0.9% failed for unknown reasons. Nest fate depended strongly on fencing. 78.1% of nests with a fence time of > 75% hatched. 53.2% of nests which were not fenced or only part of the time were predated (Table 2).

From the incubation models (see Table 3 for all coefficient estimates), we found that hatching success depended strongly on fencing and on the date of nest start (Fig. 3A). While non-fenced nests had almost no chance of hatching, independent of the date, fenced nests had a high hatching success if nest start was before the end of April. Thereafter, hatching success continuously decreased to very low values for nests initiated after mid-May. This was mainly due to a concomitant increase of the probability that the nest was abandoned by the female before hatching (Fig. 3C). Predation probability on the other hand remained largely constant across the season (Fig. 3B). Failure of hatching in non-fenced nests was mainly due to predation and, to a lower degree, due to abandonment (Table 2).

In the raw data, overall hatching success was between about 60 and 80% for most of the years, but somewhat lower 2016–2019 due to increased predation events (Supporting information). According to the model, hatching success for fenced nests decreased, from 0.93 (95% uncertainty interval 0.83–0.98) in 2006 to 0.64 (0.42–0.81) in 2021 (Supporting information). Predation did not show a marked trend over the years (Supporting information), while nest abandonment appears to have slightly increased in fenced nests and decreased in only partly or not fenced nests (Supporting information).

Effects of the mean number of active neighbouring nests (within 50 m) were equivocal. Hatching success for fenced nests may have increased somewhat with more neighbours, but decreased for only partly or not fenced nests (Supporting information). However, for fenced nests there were up to 16 neighbours, while unfenced nests were mostly isolated (see methods), hence we have no data to make a statement about the effect of having many neighbours on unprotected nests. Nests that were protected only part of the time showed, if anything, no or a decreasing effect of the number of neighbours on hatching success (Supporting information). A question was whether larger aggregations of lapwing nests would help to reduce predation. This was not the case in our data, where predation appeared independent of the number of neighbours, albeit with very large uncertainty for unfenced nests (Supporting information). Abandonment probability increased with more neighbours in unfenced nests according to the model (Supporting information), but again, uncertainty was large.

Hatching success was highest at intermediate values of the weather parameter considered for the hatching period, the time without rain during incubation (Fig. 4). Predation appears to have increased during suboptimal weather (dry or wet; Supporting information). A similar effect of weather was observed on abandonment, albeit with a stronger effect of dry (compared to wet) weather increasing abandonment (Supporting information).

Hatching success was similar in most field types (Supporting information). The estimate for extensive meadow was much lower but due to the uncertainty of this estimate, conclusions are difficult. Maize and wet meadow showed the largest hatching success (mean estimate close to 90%). Regarding maize, however, this prediction is of limited value, because the estimate in Supporting information is for a maize field at a mean date, i.e. 10 April (mean of all nests, see Table 1), while most maize fields are sown later so that most nests in maize fields are late nests (Fig. 2). In a model not correcting for date, i.e. predicting for a maize field at an average date of maize field nests, the hatching success is considerably lower (blue estimates in the Supporting information). On the other hand, abandonment of nests in maize fields was low if corrected for date but high if not corrected for date (light blue estimates in the Supporting information).

Fledging success

For 1566 chicks a capture history could be determined (mostly ringed chicks, but in the later years also non-ringed chicks of families with a ringed female). 1027 chicks were re-encountered at least once, 437 were observed after fledging (i.e. post-fledge of the same year or in a later year, Supporting information), and an additional 75 chicks were known to have fledged from re-encounters outside our study area or because they were observed to be able to fly already around day 30. 719 of the 1566 chicks were known to have died almost certainly before fledging, because they were observed dead, or because (for 424) they were observed only once (i.e. at ringing) and only before age 15 days. For chicks with unknown status during the post-fledging period the model estimated whether they were alive or not. Together with those known alive, we evaluated a fledging success of 37.4% [95% uncertainty interval: 36.5–38.4%] across all 1566 chicks (Fig. 5).

In the naive model using the fencing status based on the raw data, the estimated survival inside and outside the fence was not very different, especially also not for the first days, such that an estimated fledging probability of 51% (95% uncertainty interval: [38; 65%]) resulted for a chick that was

Table 2. Number of nests depending on fencing (rows) and nest fate (columns). The proportion of the time the nest was fenced (from egg laying to hatching or egg loss) is categorized into four bins (four rows). Italic numbers are the percentage value per row.

Fence time	Hatched	Predated	Abandoned	Destroyed	Flooded	Unknown	Total
0–25%	33	92	35	8	4	1	173
25–50%	11	10	18	0	0	0	39
50–75%	93	12	16	1	0	1	123
75–100%	531	53	86	2	1	7	680
Total	668	167	155	11	5	9	1015

Table 3. Parameter estimates from three additive logistic models with the binary outcomes hatching, predation and abandonment. For covariates, the transformation is given (z = centred and scaled to 1 SD, lin. and quad. = linear and quadratic effects, log = natural logarithm, a.s. = arcus-sinus square-root). The model estimates are given with the 2.5 and 97.5% quantiles from the marginal posterior distribution (95% uncertainty interval). A smoother was used to model the effect of date (in interaction with fence). Baseline level for field type = cultivated field. See Table 1 for variable definitions.

Parameter	Transf.	Hatching	Predation	Abandonment
Intercept		0.00 [−0.52; 0.54]	−2.81 [−3.48; −2.16]	−1.85 [−2.31; −1.38]
Fence time	lin., z	2.16 [1.63; 2.67]	−1.19 [−1.54; −0.86]	−0.72 [−1.03; −0.41]
	quad., z	−0.77 [−1.04; −0.50]	0.38 [0.10; 0.66]	0.10 [−0.12; 0.34]
Year	z	−0.14 [−0.48; 0.22]	−0.03 [−0.53; 0.46]	−0.06 [−0.39; 0.26]
Weather	lin., z	−0.45 [−0.70; −0.20]	0.25 [−0.01; 0.50]	0.55 [0.31; 0.78]
	quad., z	−0.71 [−0.92; −0.50]	0.62 [0.39; 0.85]	0.26 [0.07; 0.44]
Neighbours	log, z	−0.57 [−0.88; −0.25]	−0.06 [−0.42; 0.30]	0.12 [−0.17; 0.40]
Field type				
Fallow, stubbles		−0.26 [−0.79; 0.26]	0.00 [−0.74; 0.76]	0.30 [−0.30; 0.89]
Lapwing fallow		−0.22 [−0.82; 0.38]	0.60 [−0.27; 1.48]	0.55 [−0.18; 1.28]
Maize		0.24 [−0.37; 0.85]	0.62 [−0.10; 1.35]	−0.14 [−0.76; 0.45]
Extensive meadow		−1.47 [−2.70; −0.26]	1.71 [0.50; 2.96]	0.39 [−1.20; 2.02]
Wet meadow		0.25 [−0.55; 1.06]	−0.52 [−1.86; 0.86]	0.67 [−0.27; 1.60]
Year × fence	z / z	−0.56 [−0.79; −0.32]	0.06 [−0.20; 0.32]	0.42 [0.22; 0.63]
Neighbours × fence	log, z / z	1.02 [0.58; 1.45]	−0.13 [−0.47; 0.20]	−0.54 [−0.84; −0.24]
s(date) F × 1		−1.99 [−3.71; −0.25]	0.06 [−0.24; 0.35]	0.82 [0.56; 1.09]

always within a fence, and of 41% [30; 56%] for a chick always outside a fence (assuming, for both fence statuses, average values for year, date, and weather; note that an average weather value was associated with an above-average survival, Supporting information). As stated in the methods and discussed below, these are most likely biased estimates because those chicks dying during the first days probably often left the fence and were predated, while their last fence status was ‘inside fence’ as most nests were fenced (only 10.6% of young chicks seen only once had fence status ‘outside fence’). Using different scenarios of the proportion of young chick that left the fence unnoticed before being predated (or otherwise died), the estimated survival changed substantially (Table 4). For comparison, values from Rickenbach et al. (2011) are given in Table 4, too. Based on our judgement regarding young chick survival, we here present the survival curves for the scenario with 50% of the young chicks (that were seen only once) set to ‘outside fence’ (augmenting the 10.6–50%, Fig. 5). Survival curves for other scenarios are given in the supporting information.

Field observations allowed for a precise estimate of the mean number of chicks hatched per breeding pair (including replacement broods) per year. This value was roughly stable across the years (open circles in Fig. 6). The number of fledged chicks estimated by the fledging model was, depending on the year, about 8–75% larger than the value observed directly in the field (triangles compared with grey dots in Fig. 6). The number fledged per breeding pair is often seen as the key demographic parameter for survival of lapwing populations in Europe, with a value of at least 0.8 needed for a stable population (Peach et al. 1994); this value was reached in our population in the years 2010–2015, but it was mostly below for the years before and after (Fig. 6).

At intermediate weather, i.e. at intermediate proportions of dry and warm (> 15°C) weather, fledging probability was maximal (Supporting information). Furthermore, fledging

was highest for earlier nests (Supporting information), albeit the effect was much less pronounced than for hatching probability. Finally, we observed substantial variation in the mean fledging probability among years (Supporting information).

Discussion

Nest fate depended strongly on date of breeding and on fencing. Unfenced nests had a hatching probability of less than 10% throughout, independent on nest date, suffering from a predation probability of around 50%. For fenced nests, there was a clear negative effect of lay date caused by the abandoning probability gradually going up to 80% over the season. Loss of nests by agricultural activity was very low due to close cooperation with the farmers.

In our study area, lapwings preferred habitats with low height and sparse vegetation: fallows, wet meadows and maize fields. ‘Lapwing fallows’, established specifically to provide suitable breeding habitat, were successful in some years. Due to several reasons (predators breaking into fences, warm winters favouring rapid vegetation growth on the fallow fields), however, breeding pairs shifted over the years to other sites within the study area. Maize is known to be an important breeding habitat in Europe, as it offers bare ground until late in the breeding season. In the Netherlands, almost half of the population breeds in maize fields (Schekkerman et al. 2002). In our study area, maize fields were often chosen for replacement clutches, when other cultures were growing too tall. However, maize grows fast and many nests on maize were abandoned before hatching as growing plants started to impair the field of vision for the breeding female. Hence, in our study site, it seems clear that due to the general growth of the vegetation and especially of maize, we see a strong increase of abandonment across the season; the willingness to abandon a clutch also likely increases in the course of the

Figure 3. Effects of the date of nest start (1 March to 1 June) and nest fencing on hatching success (A), predation probability (B), and abandonment probability (C). Estimates and 95% uncertainty intervals (only for 0 and 100% for better readability) from the three 'incubation models' (text) are given. Nest start = 5 days before first egg was laid, fence = proportion of time the nest was fenced between egg-laying and hatching or eggloss. Estimates are only drawn across the range of dates available per class of fencing ($\pm 10\%$ around labelled value). Other predictors in the model were set to their mean (e.g. 73% of nest time with fence, nest start date 10 April), the field type to 'lapwing fallow'. For sample sizes, see Table 2.

season. In the years 2018–2021, an increasing number of nests were on a 2.2 ha fenced field managed for conservation (86 of the 97 nests of field type 'wet meadow'), with low vegetation and areas with shallow water in spring and heaps of earth piled-up specifically for lapwing nest sites. This one single field harboured 18, 23 and 25 pairs in 2019–2021, representing a density of 8.2, 10.5 and 11.4 pairs/ha, which is one of the highest reported (maximal values compiled by Shrubbs 2007, p. 118, are 10.8, 6.7 and 5.6 pairs/ha). The

Figure 4. Effect of weather (with 95% uncertainty interval) on hatching success. Available data (nests) are depicted as a rug.

habitat on this 2.2 ha field appeared to be ideal as reflected by the high breeding density. However, this high density also led to various problems such that, in the end, numbers of fledged young per pair were insufficient. The high density forced many (probably subordinate) females to leave the fence with their chicks once they had hatched. We also fenced the neighbouring fields, but feeding opportunities there were probably less optimal, especially during dry periods. Also, the concentration of a substantial part of the population on one field may pose a cluster risk. This was especially evident in 2022 (after the focal period for the analyses presented here) when a fox broke into the fence and reduced hatching success to around 30%.

The field described above is adjacent to a field road with leisure visitors, dog walkers (dog leash compulsory in the area), cyclists, and photographers attracted by the lapwing colony. Some nests were less than 10 m from the road and the hedge with large trees on the other side of the road. Lapwings normally keep more distance to woods and other vertical

Figure 5. Estimated chick survival curve inside and outside a fence according to the scenario where we augmented the proportion of young chicks (seen only once) outside a fence from 10.6% (raw data) to 50% (text). The area around the curves are 95% uncertainty intervals.

Table 4. Estimated survival of the first step (3-day survival) and to fledging (33-day survival) (with 95% uncertainty interval) depending on the proportion of young chicks that were outside a fence when they died (20, 50 and 80% are scenarios calculated due the certain underestimation of this value in the raw data).¹For inside fence, Fig. 3–4 suggest an almost 100% survival. Based on values measured out of their Fig. 3: 12-h-survival outside fence estimate for youngest chicks (1–5 days) 0.970 during the day \times 0.871 during the night, extrapolated to a 3-day survival. ²Based on their Fig. 3 (averaged across a chick time of 33 days).

Proportion of young chicks outside fence	Survival day 1–3 to 4–6 (3-day survival)		Survival to fledging (33-day survival)	
	In fence	Outside fence	In fence	Outside fence
10.6% (raw data)	0.848 [0.775; 0.925]	0.821 [0.771; 0.873]	0.51 [0.38; 0.63]	0.42 [0.30; 0.56]
20%	0.992 [0.851; 0.975]	0.781 [0.734; 0.829]	0.58 [0.44; 0.71]	0.36 [0.26; 0.47]
50%	0.988 [0.962; 0.998]	0.736 [0.693; 0.781]	0.68 [0.54; 0.81]	0.29 [0.21; 0.40]
80%	0.996 [0.986; 0.999]	0.710 [0.667; 0.753]	0.74 [0.60; 0.85]	0.26 [0.18; 0.36]
Rickenbach et al. (2011)	$\sim 1.000^{(1)}$	0.603 ⁽¹⁾	0.287 ⁽²⁾	0.015 ⁽²⁾

structures, because these increase their vulnerability to avian and ground predators (Berg et al. 1992, Sheldon et al. 2007, Bertholdt et al. 2017, but no such effect found by Kamp et al. 2015). Fencing of this ideal habitat apparently favoured high breeding densities and habituation to humans and even to dogs (which did not alert the breeding lapwings).

Predator-exclusion fencing can improve reproductive success substantially (Smith et al. 2011, Malpas et al. 2013, Werner et al. 2017, Cimiotti et al. 2022). Our data on hatching probability confirmed this clearly. Red foxes are very common in our study area. From field observations (e.g. of fox tracks, search behaviour in fields with lapwings, and a camera trap field study in 2009 by M. Ott using chicken baits, where 81% of removals at unfenced sites were by foxes), we strongly assume that the fox is the main predator in our study area, precluding sufficient reproduction in the absence of fences.

Figure 6. Number of hatched young per breeding pair (circles; including potential replacement clutches), number of fledged young as observed in the field (triangles) and number fledged as estimated by the fledging model (grey dots with 95% uncertainty intervals; estimates for 2006–2007 from Rickenbach et al. (2011); no estimates for 2008, 2009, 2016 and 2018 due to non-sufficient observation efforts in these years). Grey bar = 0.8–1 fledged per breeding pair as a minimal number needed for population stability as suggested by Peach et al. (1994).

The study area offers ideal habitat for foxes, food availability is generally high all year round and due to the destruction of the former marshland, foxes have free access to nests of ground-breeding birds. Regarding chick survival, strong predation outside fences and at night in our study area has been shown by Rickenbach et al. (2011) based on 159 radio-tagged chicks in 2006 and 2007 (bottom row in Table 4). In our present analysis, involving 1566 chicks, the fence effect is more difficult to pinpoint. Many chicks were only seen once just after hatching and were lost between two observation days, and regularly, all chicks of a family disappeared in the same night. Our scenarios with more chicks leaving the fence unnoticed before dying suggest more realistic survival curves in our views. Note that the scenarios only differ regarding the allocation of survived chicks to within vs outside fence (not to the overall estimated survival of our 1566 chicks, which was around 37%). Also note that by using a mean weather value, which is associated with a high survival, rather large survival values were estimated. This alone, however, cannot explain our substantially higher estimates compared to those found by Rickenbach et al. (2011) in 2006 and 2007, which may have been generally unfavourable years (compare higher reproductive success in the following years, Fig. 6), with virtually no survival of chicks outside fences.

Using our scenarios, the fledging model predicted a chick survival of about 60–70% inside and 30% outside fence (given mean weather, date and year values). For hatching success, the difference was more accentuated, with a very high value inside and a very low value outside fence. Since fences only exclude ground predators but not aerial predators, we conclude that aerial predators appear to be of little importance regarding egg loss in our study area. Chicks, on the other hand, suffered substantial mortality by mammalian as well as aerial predators (Rickenbach et al. 2011; direct observations of aerial predation were by carrion crow, red kite, black kite *Milvus migrans*, common kestrel, and common buzzard *Buteo buteo*). Other factors taking their toll on chicks were cold and rainy weather and lack of food e.g. during dry periods (starvation, hypothermia). These factors act independently of the fence status and were estimated to amount to around 6% by Rickenbach et al. (2011), in addition to about 6% chick loss due to agricultural activity (mainly outside fences).

If a loss of 30–40% of chicks within fence is a good estimate, and if around 10% are due to other causes than

predation, around 20–30% of chicks were lost to predators not excluded by fences (on both sides of the fence; in our judgement, mainly aerial predators, but also stoat). Outside fences, with a total loss of around 70% (and likely some additional loss through agricultural fieldworks compared to within fence), we estimate a roughly similar toll of chicks to aerial and to mammalian predators. Mason et al. (2018) also reported comparable losses due to the two classes of predators (of 179 predated chicks: 37% mammalian, 28% avian, 35% unattributable). Eglington et al. (2009) found that avian predation of chicks probably predominated, while Schekkerman et al. (2009) and Teunissen et al. (2008) observed the opposite (though detection probability of a mammalian vs avian predation might differ in these studies based on radio-tagged chicks).

In a semi-colonial breeder, we could expect hatching success to increase with the number of neighbours. For only partly or not fenced nests, we found the opposite trend, while fully fenced nests showed high hatching probability even with no neighbours (Supporting information; note that our conclusions are limited by the fact that we don't have unfenced nests with many neighbours). The suggested negative effect of neighbours does not seem to be caused by increased predation of (small) aggregations of lapwings, since predation probability did not show such a signal (Supporting information). Rather, abandonment seems to have increased (Supporting information), which we cannot easily interpret (e.g. why would intraspecific aggression, leading to increased abandonment, be limited to partly fenced and unfenced nests?). On the other hand, the independence of hatching success from the number of neighbours for fenced nests suggests that there was no strong colony effect on egg loss, neither a positive effect (more lapwings defend better), nor a negative effect (honey-pot effect attracting predators to larger aggregations). Density effects on predation have been reported by Baines (1990), Berg et al. (1992), MacDonald and Bolton (2008) and Eglington et al. (2009), while Kamp et al. (2015) observed less predation with higher breeding density only on brownfields (industrial fallow areas), but the opposite on arable land and pastures; Galbraith (1988) found no clear effect of density. Possibly, in our study site, crows and grey heron *Ardea cinerea*, the main potential aerial egg predators, find enough other food in the agricultural landscape.

An increasing lapwing population and learning by predators to associate fences with food (eggs and chicks) could lead to an increasing predation rate over the years (colony as a 'honey pot', Eglington et al. 2009, Malpas et al. 2013). Overall, such an effect was not obvious in our data where predation remained roughly constant (with time as well as density). On the ideal-habitat field described above, predation increased 2019–2022. This may give some support for the honey pot theory, but on the other hand, 2022 was a year with a very low availability of rodents in the area (pers. observation by us and farmers), forcing foxes to search for alternative food. We observed a slight increase of abandonment of fenced nests over the years. This may be due to two very aggressive pairs of coots *Fulica atra*, breeding in the ideal-habitat field. Coots attacked

breeding lapwings and chicks, stole eggs and, in one case, even built a nest on top of an active lapwing nest, killing the eggs.

Hatching success as well as fledging success were highest at intermediate values of the weather parameter considered (proportion of dry, and for fledging also warm, hours). Rain is essential to ensure soil moisture and thereby food availability (Matter 1982, Eglington 2008, Bellebaum and Bock 2009). Too much rain might reduce hatching success due to cooling of the clutch during breeding breaks that the adults use for foraging, or due to flooding. Fledging success could be reduced by rain because chicks need to be brooded more often, resulting in shorter foraging periods (Beintema and Visser 1989b). On the other hand, food availability is reduced during dry conditions, leading to longer breeding breaks which increases predation risk of the eggs and to a reduction of fitness of chicks (Johansson et al. 1998).

For a stable lapwing population, about 0.8–1.0 fledglings per breeding pair are needed (Galbraith 1988, Peach et al. 1994; 0.6–0.8 according to Malpas et al. 2013, 0.8–1.6 according to Roodbergen et al. 2012). This value was reached shortly after fencing started in most years until 2015 (Fig. 6). 2016 was a very bad year due to adverse weather during the breeding season. Thereafter, productivity increased again but was mostly below 0.8–1.0 fledgling per breeding pair. This was likely due to insufficient humidity during the time of chick raising (no or few paddles or areas with wet soils available due to weather conditions), but also due to predation (especially in 2022 and 2023). The development of the productivity is mirrored in the size of the local population, which increased from 15 breeding pairs in 2005 to a maximum of 60 pairs in 2015 and 2016 but decreased to 39 pairs in 2021. Another factor potentially responsible for the reduced productivity was the reduced availability of open fields (e.g. maize stubbles) as a consequence of changes in the agricultural practice after 2013 ('good agricultural practice' with measures against erosion such as no-till, intertillage, and catch crop). Nevertheless, despite the somewhat receding population, several isolated breeding attempts of 1–2 pairs in the wider area (10 km) have been registered in recent years of individuals originating from our study area (colour ringed birds).

Our study confirms the findings of others, that the lapwing population in Switzerland is heavily dependent on intensive conservation measures, particularly fencing (Ritschard 2021). Lapwings show high breeding site-fidelity and are highly philopatric (Thompson et al. 1994), hence local conservation efforts may be successful. But the needed efforts are high, including guidance of agricultural activities (delayed farming, subsidies, set-aside of fallows, etc.), nest protection from agricultural fieldwork, close observation of the activities of the lapwings and efficient fencing of breeding sites, as well as habitat improvements which often is the most costly and controversial measure due to competing interests with agricultural productivity.

Apart from fencing, a key factor would be to provide areas with wet soils or puddles (Bellebaum and Bock 2009), a challenge given the increasing frequency of dry summers. In our area, there is an upcoming discussion regarding the future of

the drainage system that is in increasingly bad shape. Taking habitat requirements of lapwings into account for the future water management may create opportunities for this species to breed successfully, as shown elsewhere in similarly intensively used regions (Wilson et al. 2004, Cimiotti et al. 2015, Kamp et al. 2015, Franks et al. 2018).

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Author contributions

Pius Korner: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Simon Hohl:** Data curation (equal); Funding acquisition (supporting); Investigation (equal); Methodology (supporting); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Petra Horch:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (equal).

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Data availability statement

Data are available from the Zenodo Digital Repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10566074> (Korner et al. 2024).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

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